

UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLES USAGE IN METEOROLOGY FIELD

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The accuracy of weather forecasts is important, however, it is difficult to collect high-quality and modern atmospheric data, since the weather is a chaotic, constantly changing system. Drones have become a possible alternative, as they can be deployed at any time, equipped with various sensors and piloted based on information obtained from a weather station. The relevance of the article is determined by the need to study the use of drones as meteorological devices.

Keywords: drones technology, weather forecast, atmospheric conditions.

Unmanned aerial vehicles today perform many functions: they deliver cargo, track weather conditions, and fight weeds and pest insects. In the field of meteorology, exploitation has not yet begun, since this topic is relatively new both abroad and in the CIS countries. The novelty of the article is due to the fact that there's no generalizing scientific study on the use of drones in weather forecasting in Kazakhstan.

The global market for services using unmanned aerial vehicles (drones) exceeds \$127 billion, according to a study by PricewaterhouseCoopers. Infrastructure has become the largest area of use of drones (this means energy and oil and gas, as well as roads and railways) – experts at \$45.2 billion estimate the potential cost of drone services in this area. This is followed by agriculture (\$32.4 billion), transport (\$13 billion) and security (\$10 billion).

There are also extensive opportunities for the use of drones in the media and entertainment industry, in the insurance business, in the field of telecommunications services and in the mining industry [7].

In 2018, Kazakhstan launched “KazTechInnovations”, the first factory in the republic for the development and production of unmanned aerial vehicles. The plant for the production of Kazakhstani drones is located 20 kilometers from Almaty, on the territory of a special economic zone – the Alatau Park of Innovative Technologies.

Physicists, electronics and production workers claim that they did not copy other people's developments and did not attract development partners from abroad. They have a team, which consists of extra-class specialists. A few years ago, they decided to create drones "from scratch" and strictly adhere to this course. Interestingly, at the plant, gliders are treated not as aircraft, but as robotic systems with certain functionality. This is probably why in the team you will not meet employees who have received the traditional education of "aircraft models" and "aircraft technicians" for this area [3].

The most popular commercial drones that are used in Kazakhstan today are produced in Russia and China. Most are shaped like a flying wing. However, the company believes that this form is too unstable for difficult Kazakh conditions: a sudden gust of wind can cause a critical disruption. And this is a serious drawback for

specialized aircraft. Therefore, Kazakh engineers, together with military specialists of the «National Defense University», chose the classic airframe construction scheme for a military aircraft, which consists of a fuselage, wing and remote tail. Such a mechanism has better handling, which means more chances to get out of a sudden roll. Central Asian countries such as Uzbekistan, Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan will be primarily interested in such complexes, because in these states the niche of reconnaissance UAVs is not yet occupied.

Aviation in agriculture is an indispensable thing: without it, the fight against pests and diseases of cultivated plants would turn into a battle with windmills. However, the services of "corn workers" are not affordable for all farmers. One flight of small aviation costs at least 500 thousand tenge. The use of drones has already been recognized as a cheaper and more promising option for helping farmers [8].

The market volume for accompanying agricultural business is simply huge. It's about billions of dollars. So far, this sector is dominated by foreign companies. But already this year, KazTechInnovations will take a closer look at this market and will focus, among other things, on commercial aviation. The task of going abroad is very difficult, but they will go in this direction.

By April 2021, it was planned to complete flight tests of two prototypes of commercial drones at once, similar in shape, but different in use. Practical launches will help identify management errors and fix them. After that, the drones will go into mass production. This enterprise can produce up to 150 military drones per year, which will reliably protect the sky and land of Kazakhstan from any invasions [3].

RSE "Kazhydromet" is the only legally responsible body that has the right to official information service of any organizations with storm warnings about impending dangerous and elemental phenomena of nature on the territory of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The subject of the Enterprise's activity is environmental monitoring, meteorological and hydrological monitoring using the state monitoring network. The purpose of the Enterprise's activities is to obtain reliable hydrometeorological information, improve the quality of hydro-meteorological and agrometeorological forecasts and information on the state of the environment, collect and

summarize data obtained during systematic observations on the state observation network [1].

The company was formed in 1922, but the first meteorological observations in Kazakhstan were recorded more than 170 years ago – in Kazalinsk, Verny, Akmolinsk and Semipalatinsk. Today, there are 35 stations in the Republic of Kazakhstan with a hundred-year series of observations. The activities of the RSE "Kazhydromet" are quite extensive – this is not only forecasting weather conditions, but also hydrological, agrometeorological forecasts, as well as monitoring the state of the environment. Now Kazhydromet has 15 branches in each region of the Republic of Kazakhstan, including in Aktau, the total staff number is more than 3 thousand people. Branch has 102 employees.

Meteorological observations are carried out at special stations, of which they have 341 in Kazakhstan. Every three hours at meteorological stations, that is, eight times a day, a meteorologist technician conducts observations at a certain time, taking readings from instruments on temperature and humidity, wind speed and direction, atmospheric pressure, visibility and cloud cover, notes weather phenomena. For example, now the technician would note cloudy weather, determine and record how many points are cloudy, the height of the lower border of the clouds. Moreover, observations of cloud cover are often carried out visually. Then these and other meteorological parameters, atmospheric phenomena are noted in a special meteorological book. Over time, part of the meteorologist's work is automated, modern instruments and electronic books appear, but the foundations of meteorological observations remain. Like decades ago, the meteorologist technician continuously monitors the development of weather events and cloud cover and every three hours records the values of all meteorological characteristics at a special site. Moreover, this is very important, because all observations are carried out synchronously around the world. The results of such observations are necessary to make a future forecast. At the end of observations, a telegram is formed, which with encoded data is sent to the communication center to the branch, from there – to the central collection system. 274 stations send such telegrams to the world data center for international exchange to calculate the global forecast. As a result, all this falls on the synoptic cards that the forecaster receives.

But this is not enough either. To develop a weather forecast, you need to know what is happening in the atmosphere at a significant altitude – 25-30 km. For this, there are nine aerological stations on the territory of Kazakhstan, which launch radiosondes twice a day – at 06:00 and at 18:00. These are small devices with special sensors that rise into the atmosphere on special balls filled with light gas, and also record certain readings – wind speed and direction, air temperature and humidity.

Weather forecasters analyze the information that comes from satellites from neighbor teams from Uzbekistan, Russia and other countries. As for observations in the Mangistau region, there are seven traditional meteorological stations, automatic meteorological stations – 16 units (seven of them under traditional

MS). There are seven marine hydrometeorological posts in the region.

In addition to hydrometeorological monitoring, Kazhydromet monitors pollution of atmospheric air, sea water, soil, bottom sediments, as well as exposure dose and gamma radiation. In the region, seven posts, of which five are automatic, two manual posts and one ecological mobile laboratory carry out monitoring of atmospheric air pollution [5].

The problem of long-term weather forecasts is one of the most pressing and yet complex problems of natural history. Despite a significant expansion of ideas about physical processes, an increase in the amount and improvement in the quality of meteorological information, the justifiability of long-term weather forecasts has not yet met the requirements of the national economy. Moreover, to the greatest extent this applies to forecasts of extremes of meteorological values, informative whose value is highest. The relevance of monthly and seasonal weather forecasts is determined by the fact that if they are justified by 70% or more, they could significantly contribute to improving the efficiency of production of agriculture, energy and other nature-intensive sectors of the national economy. That is why the improvement of existing and the creation of new weather forecast methods for the month and season remains. In addition, apparently, will remain relevant and necessary for a long time.

The main goal is to study the spatial-temporal patterns of large-scale weather-forming processes and develop an operational technology for long-term weather forecasts of great advance, all stages of making predictions in which are automated. To achieve this goal, the following main scientific and practical tasks have been set and solved:

- generalization and systematization of the results of studies contained in the extensive literature on the problem of long-term forecasting;
- studied the distributions of predictors and predictors and assessed the possibility of using approximation functions in long-term weather forecasts;
- the spatial statistical structure of meteorological fields on the plain and in the mountains was studied, and their accuracy was assessed;

The work has an applied and theoretical orientation. To implement it, materials from the Kazhydromet ground observation system, as well as synoptic bulletins of the USSR Hydrometeorological Center, were involved. In addition, the daily fields of objective analysis of ground temperature, ground pressure, temperature on isobaric surfaces of 850 hPa, absolute geopotential on surfaces of 850, 700, 500, 300, 100 hPa across the northern hemisphere for 00 hours of average Greenwich time. Specified at the nodes of the regular grid of 5 x 5, received through the global telecommunications system from the US National Meteorological Center, were used. To process and analyze the data, methods of decomposing their fields according to empirical orthogonal functions (EOF) and Chebyshev polynomials, spectral, correlation and regression analyses, various methods of objective classification of natural objects, as well as a system of probability Pearson curves and approximation splines were used.

The degree of reliability of the sample indicators was confirmed by calculations confidence limits. To determine the characteristics of PVFZ and inter-latitude exchange indices, algorithms were developed and special programs were compiled. The processing used in the work of the information was carried out on the EU computer and PC.

The classification of the main methods and principles of weather forecasting for the month and season by statistical methods is given. Depending on the statistical apparatus used, five methods were identified: regression, analogues, probabilistic, extrapolational and discretionary analysis. The laws of distribution of predictors and predictants have been studied. To approximate empirical distributions, spline functions and a system of Pearson probability curves were used. Studies of the distributions of predictants, grouped depending on the values of predictors, and their approximation by theoretical functions make it possible to determine the error of any gradation of the predicted value, which is important for the complexation of forecasts made by various methods [4].

An unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) "Tsimlyanin" was built in Russia, designed for meteorological research and weather monitoring in the Arctic latitudes. The drone was designed by specialists from the Moscow Aviation Institute (MAI) and the A.M. Obukhov Institute of Atmospheric Physics of the Russian Academy of Sciences. The device has already passed flight tests, the press service of the Moscow Aviation Institute reports.

The drone has a vertical launch: it does not need special runways, which facilitates its use in the Arctic. The soft and controlled flight mode reduces the risk of damage to expensive weather devices installed on board. The wingspan of the drone is 2.4 meters, weight – 1.5 kilograms. The device can be in the air for about an hour, and its maximum speed reaches 20 meters per second. In addition, Tsimlyanin is equipped with an autopilot function and is able to independently fly along a predetermined route.

The drone is planned to be used to study the turbulent structures of the boundary layer of the atmosphere. In the future, the development can be used to create a meteorological monitoring network in the Arctic, as well as to quickly track and predict the ice situation along the Northern Sea Route and in the waters of the northern ports of Russia.

Unmanned aerial vehicles are starting to be used in meteorology, since data from aerological sensing at different altitudes obtained from them provide more complete information than point observations at meteorological stations. The use of drones in hard-to-reach areas, where a few meteorological and aerological stations are located far from each other (this is typical for the Arctic), is especially important.

Note that the increasing pace of development of Arctic territories requires an increase in the reliability of forecasts of such adverse and dangerous weather events as storm waves, gusty winds, cloudiness, glaciation and precipitation. It was for this specific task that the Tsimlyanin unmanned aerial vehicle was created. The main purpose of the device is to measure with a

high frequency of humidity, temperature and certain wind parameters at different altitudes within 1.5 kilometers of the surface of the earth or sea ice [2].

In the United Arab Emirates, a modern strategy of causing rain in places with a deficiency of precipitation utilizing unmanned aerial vehicles is being explored. UAVs planned and made at the University of Bath, UK, carry an electricity that's discharged into the cloud, giving cloud beads the exceptionally thrust they ought to adhere together and drop as rain.

This can be one of the primary examples when researchers utilized unmanned ethereal machines in an endeavor to fortify precipitation from clouds. Earlier to this, strategies of inciting precipitation in dry nations included the use of air ship or rockets seeding cloud areas with particles, such as, for case, silver iodide. Analysts within the gadgets and electrical designing office at University of Bath have created both unmanned air vehicles and a few of the hardware.

The primary UAV flights in the Emirates are supposed to start within another few months. Water deficiencies are a genuine issue in numerous nations within the Middle Eastern world. The normal precipitation within the Emirates is around 100 mm per year, and the nation is becoming drier and drier as temperatures increase due to worldwide warming. Researchers trust that the innovation created for the venture can be utilized to stimulate precipitation, and hopefully it will work in conjunction with existing strategies to maximize cloud seeding proficiency [6].

Overall, it is difficult to accurately predict weather, since the it is a chaotic, constantly changing system and collect high quality and modern atmospheric data can be troublesome. By studying the possibility of using drones to predict various weather conditions in Kazakhstan, the necessity of using drones as meteorological devices in Kazakhstan could be determine.

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